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Advanced materials (AdMa) are evolving to offer new materials for different applications ranging from food to medicine and electronics. Addressing the safety and the sustainability of materials, in general, at an early stage of their design requires adequate methods for risk and sustainability assessment. The current risk assessment framework for chemicals and nanomaterials cannot cover AdMa. In this perspective we highlight the challenges the toxicology community might face in optimal design and efficient use of the frameworks for AdMa and predicting their (environmental) risk. We performed an analysis of the existing knowledge pertaining AdMa and their physicochemical properties to propose some criteria for the classification of AdMa to facilitate generating toxicological data for risk assessment.

“Advanced materials” and the challenges on the horizon for testing their (eco)toxicity and assessing their hazard

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Abstract

“Advanced Materials” (AdMa) represent the next technology frontier. According to the European Union, AdMa are materials that feature a series of exceptional properties or functionalities compared to conventional materials. Considering the progress made in design and application of AdMa, their adverse effects are still largely unknown whilst this is critical for assessing their environmental and human health risk. In this perspective, we first summarize the available definitions/descriptions and categorizations that cover AdMa and evaluate their adequacy from a toxicological point of view. We further describe the challenges and outlook on the toxicology of AdMa and propose solutions to tackle some of the challenges. Criteria related to which AdMa might induce hazards are discussed and used to propose a starting point of how to address AdMa in legal frameworks that consider human and environmental risks. Finally, we highlight the benefit of classification e.g. enabling differentiation between AdMa based on their properties that might induce specific hazards and facilitate a faster pathway to identify the hazard of new AdMa, which is particularly relevant for safe-by-design.

Introduction

The technology of Advanced Materials (AdMa) is still maturing as a discipline, with many new material discoveries expanding its realm. AdMa are more complex than conventional materials and cover a wide variety of materials, material combinations and material scales (including the nano-scale). They are of interest due to their novel or enhanced properties ¹ that potentially enable applications such as digital innovations, health advancement, aid in increasing energy conversion and storage ², and advanced environmental remediation potential. For example, some AdMa can function dynamically which means they have passive and active states, leading to the performance of specific tasks upon activation, e.g., catalytically active AdMa known as nanozymes. AdMa are evolving to offer seemingly endless possibilities by elaborating molecular architectures for different applications ranging from food to medicine and electronics.

Assessing the potential risks associated with use of different types of AdMa is critical. This is important not only for technological development but also to reach some of the transitions and goals of the European Green Deal ³. Indeed, the introduction of new and evolving technologies to the market to benefit society and the economy requires balancing the risks and benefits for humans and the environment. Addressing the safety and the sustainability of materials, in general, at an early stage of their design may benefit (risk) governance, but requires adequate methods for risk and sustainability assessment ⁴.

The considerations of balancing risks and benefits are therefore an important question to address if AdMa are to reach their full commercial and societal potential. However, such considerations are not starting from zero. For example, risk is calculated from exposure (the dose delivered) and hazard (how toxic the substance is). The relationships between physicochemical properties and both exposure and hazard have been widely studied for nanomaterials (NMs), which can provide information relevant to AdMa. NMs are defined based on their size (1-100 nm) (EU Commission, 2011), where the size-dependent unique properties distinguish them from their bulk counterparts. NMs could be considered as AdMa, but not all AdMa are NMs. For example, some AdMa have a size larger than the dimension proposed by the European Commission (EC) for defining NMs, such as artificial bacterial flagellum (200 nm) and two-armed nanoswimmer (200 nm). Various studies have assessed the human health and environmental risks of NMs, which facilitated some political actions, e.g. in the EU ⁵. Now, similar

concerns arise for AdMa, noting that some of these materials are already used in products with biomedical, cosmetic and electronic applications ⁶.

The current risk assessment frameworks for NMs are based on the data generated for the so-called “first generation” of NMs ⁷, where the materials are made of one main substance ⁷ (such as TiO₂, ZnO, CeO₂ and Ag), sometimes with an additional substance coating used to provide surface functionalization or colloidal stability. The question is whether such frameworks can be utilised (or adapted) for AdMa. This review focuses on hazard (rather than exposure and risk assessment), for which it is critical to understand whether the AdMa can be assessed either;

- on the basis of the known hazards of their constituents,
- on a more complex consideration of the possible toxic effects of AdMa resulting from new or enhanced function, or
- by addressing potential for different components to interact and exacerbate the toxicological response.

Toxicological data can serve to provide an early warning of risk, while a lack of such toxicological data can cause risk governance to lag behind innovation. However, the hazard assessment of AdMa might face challenges due to uncertainty on the adequacy of current test methods. The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) has conducted analyses of a number of guidance documents and test guidelines for their relevance to adequately assess the toxicity of NMs ⁸. These considerations could be adopted for some AdMa. Such considerations would need to incorporate the complexity of the materials, their properties, and their dynamic functions, which can make comparisons between AdMa and other substances difficult. Such uncertainties can also lead to a lack of clarity with respect to their consideration in legal frameworks, e.g. as NMs, substances, or as an article.

It is therefore now opportune to develop a perspective on the applicability of existing frameworks for the hazard assessment of AdMa, to see where it applies, where modifications or new approaches might be needed. Such considerations will highlight the challenges the toxicology community might face in optimal adaptation and therefore efficient use of existing frameworks for assessing AdMa hazards. We performed an analysis of the existing knowledge pertaining to AdMa and their physicochemical properties to propose some criteria for the classification of AdMa to facilitate generating toxicological data for risk assessment. We propose potential solutions that may be applicable to tackle some of the challenges anticipated for AdMa and help to assess the hazard associated with these materials by using some of the knowledge generated on NMs. We identify the knowledge gaps to be further studied and scrutinized, and we provide some recommendations for future toxicological studies of AdMa.

What are AdMa?

Several definitions or working descriptions have been proposed for AdMa (Table 1). Recently, the German Environment Agency has provided a description for AdMa for regulatory purposes ⁹. The EC uses a broad definition of “AdMa”, which includes any material that features a series of exceptional properties (mechanical, electrical, optical, magnetic, etc.) or functionalities (self-repairing, shape change, decontamination, the transformation of energy, etc.) which can be new or enhanced compared to the conventional materials ¹⁰. This

definition covers almost all materials, including all NMs and their future generations. It is worth mentioning that the OECD has launched a Steering Group on AdMa that addresses the suitability of existing safety regulatory systems. The OECD does not aim to develop an exact definition for AdMa, instead a “working description” for AdMa that falls within the scope of OECD is elaborated. Meanwhile, a technical committee of the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) is independently working on a formal definition for AdMa.

Table 1. Some of the proposed definitions for advanced materials

Proposed definition/description of AdMa	References
<i>Any material that, through the precise control of its composition and internal structure, features a series of exceptional properties (mechanical, electric, optic, magnetic, etc.) or functionalities (self-repairing, shape change, decontamination, transformation of energy, etc.) that differentiate it from the rest of the universe of materials; or one that, when transformed through advanced manufacturing techniques, features these properties or functionalities</i>	European Commission ¹⁰
<i>Materials that are rationally designed to have new or enhanced properties, and/or targeted or enhanced structural features with the objective to achieve specific or improved functional performance.</i>	OECD ¹¹
<i>Materials that are rationally designed through the precise control of their composition and internal or external structure in order to fulfil new functional requirements</i>	The German Environment Agency ⁹
<i>Materials, and their associated process technologies, with the potential to be exploited in high value-added products.</i>	UK Technology Strategy Board ¹
<i>Materials that have been developed to the point that unique functionalities have been identified and these materials now need to be made available in quantities large enough for innovators and manufacturers to test and validate in order to develop new products.</i>	¹²
<i>Materials that are specifically engineered to exhibit novel or enhanced properties that confer superior performance relative to conventional materials.</i>	¹

The German Environment Agency identified eight clusters of AdMa¹⁰ (Figure 1) based upon their structures that demonstrate their breadth of chemistry and applications, which clearly indicates the wide variety of AdMa available and under development. Here we provide some specific example of AdMa in order to exemplify this diversity and furthermore their usefulness. The first example includes multi-layered nickel–cobalt organic framework nanosheets (based on the scheme in Figure 1, this AdMa can be categorized as a composite), developed as electrode materials for energy storage¹³. Some of these materials can be switched off and on or controlled remotely, which defines them as smart AdMa or smart NMs⁶. As another example: nanoscale

bending-sensitive and optically transparent pressure sensors have been fabricated using composite nanofibers¹⁴. Many other NMs, e.g. ionic polymer–metal composites, carbon nanotube composites, deformable polymer-based systems and biological molecular motors, have been fabricated so that these can be activated with a specific stimulus, such as pH, light, or temperature^{7 15}. Interesting examples are NMs consisting of an elastic polymer network and a molecular switch, which can change their structure from ribbon to a tight coil, then back to a ribbon when activated by light¹⁶, and nanorobots which are currently being extensively researched and developed for medical applications⁴. Using advanced polymers or hybrid advanced materials, we might also encounter advanced plastics in the future that can release smart microplastics and nanoplastics into the environment.

When considering the hazards of AdMa, the mode of action through which AdMa induce toxicity is not yet understood. Furthermore, we can not assume that the hazards of AdMa across different clusters or within each cluster (of Figure 1) will be the same. Therefore, the clustering based on the hazard might look different to what is proposed in Figure 1. This Perspective briefly describes the possible challenges associated with the hazard investigation of AdMa before considering possible categorisation strategies.

Figure 1. Clusters of Advanced Materials proposed by the German Environment Agency (modified after Giese et al. 2020) based upon their physicochemical properties and structure. This classification does not distinguish the active and passive form of the AdMa, or how the physicochemical properties relate to hazard.

Challenges surrounding the hazard assessment of AdMa.

The hazards associated with different AdMa will vary, and even for an individual AdMa they may vary during their life cycle, e.g. from the development phase to production, use, recycling and disposal. Two decades of research on NMs hazard assessment show that materials in general can induce toxicity through other modes of action compared to their chemical counterpart. Here we use this wealth of knowledge to anticipate the possible modes of action of AdMa (including a comparison to NMs), and the challenges such hazard assessments might pose. We also evaluate the challenges for extrapolation of hazard assessment of NMs to other AdMa.

1. Chemical composition is not the only influential factor

One of the main advantages of AdMa, in general, is the possibility to design them with different physicochemical properties such as size, shape, aspect ratio, hydrophobicity, etc. Systematic studies have to some extent been performed to test the influence of NM physicochemical properties on their toxicity^{17,18}. The findings have clearly confirmed that chemical composition is not the only factor influencing the toxicity of NMs, but other physicochemical properties can play important roles as well¹⁹. This most likely is also true for other AdMa, where there is further complexity, for example because of multi-elemental and functional properties which may change their uptake pathways, interactions with cells and subsequently their toxicity to organisms.

Comprehensive characterization of NMs has therefore been required both for research publications and for legislative frameworks. Such characterisation includes size distributions, surface charge, shape, surface area, impurities, etc. Such requirements are likely to be required for AdMa. This information will be useful to understand the toxicity of AdMa and link their properties to hazard. Although publications are improving, many toxicological studies still do not report a detailed characterization of the tested material, even for single element NMs, partly due to the limitations in analytical capability and availability. Without this information, accurate comparisons between data sets from different toxicological studies, laboratories, or even comparisons between species exposed to the same materials would be impossible. Hence, the scientific community is urged to include information on these characteristics both for NMs and AdMa.

2. Dynamic behaviour of AdMa

Characterization of AdMa should not be restricted to the pristine material, because of the potential complexity of transformations that influence fate and hazard. Moreover, applications of AdMa in consumer products such as food, beverage, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and feed should be considered, where they might enter organisms and move through food webs.. The transformation of materials in the body and environment are well documented. For example, studies have shown that some NMs such as Ag^{20,21} and Cu²² may dissolve relatively quickly upon entering the environment or the human body, whereas others such as TiO₂²³ and carbon nanotubes (CNT)²⁴ may last longer. Considerable effort has been made to understand the toxicity of slowly and quickly dissolving NMs and to differentiate between the toxicity of particulate and ionic or molecular forms of NMs²¹. The dissolution rate of a NM determines whether exposure to biological cells is to the intact NM, the dissolved ions/molecules or a combination of the two²⁵. For example, toxicity of CdTe/CdS quantum dots (QD) in algae was largely accounted for by dissolved Cd, while the the QD NMs were however also taken up by the cells and induced unique impacts in the cells compared to Cd²⁶. Studer et al (2010)²⁷ tested the cytotoxicity of Cu NMs stabilized with a carbon layer and CuO to HeLa cells. They concluded that the toxicity of the Cu NMs is related to the Cu ion released from the particles rather than to the particle itself. For an AdMa composed of both quickly

and slowly dissolving components, linking the biological and ecological effects to the physical form during exposure or uptake might be complicated. Azevedo et al. (2017)²⁸ investigated the toxicity of a nanostructure composed of ZnO with Ag NMs on its surface (designated as ZnO/Ag nanostructure) to *Daphnia magna*. The toxicity of ZnO and Ag NMs as single components, along with their nanostructure (ZnO/Ag) were tested. The authors concluded that neither the toxicity of the prepared mixture of ZnO and Ag nor of the ZnO/Ag nanostructure can be predicted based on the toxicity of their components alone. The toxicity of the nanostructure, showed higher toxicity than predicted on the basis of the toxicity of the individual NMs. The stability of the intact AdMa, and its propensity to break down is thus expected to cause a challenge for hazard assessment of AdMa and it is an important piece of information for further risk assessment of these materials.

To facilitate the description or understanding of which components of an AdMa drive hazard, we use Ag NMs which is coated with graphene-sheets contains Quantum Dots (QDs) as an existing example of a multi-elemental AdMa used as an antibacterial material²⁹ (Figure 2a). These AdMa consist of stable NMs (the graphene) as well as quickly soluble (Ag NMs) and slowly soluble (QD) fractions. From a toxicological perspective, the challenge is to use existing information on the single components as much as possible and complement this with additional issues e.g. related to the multicomponent nature or new or enhanced functionality (synergistic or antagonistic between any possible combinations: Figure 2a).

The considerations of dissolution are further complicated by the fact that AdMa may undergo homoaggregation and heteroaggregation in the environment. There is a wealth of knowledge on NMs showing that particles might immediately homoaggregate with themselves or heteroaggregate with background colloids in the environment³⁰. This could dramatically influence the behavior and fate of AdMa in nature. For example, upon heteroaggregation with naturally occurring iron oxide, AdMa can sediment and be removed from the aquatic phase. Moreover, aggregation might change the solubility of AdMa as was reported for NMs²².

Figure 2. a) Examples of AdMa that are released in the environment. The illustration shows Ag NMs stabilized with graphene-QD NMs. In the environment, the Ag NMs and some elements of the QDs will dissolve (at different rates), leading to the release of Ag ions and QD-related metals, whereas the graphene is stable. b-e) Illustrate smart nano-pesticides. b) Particle attachment to the surface of the plant. c) The uptake of the NMs is influenced by the physicochemical properties of the NMs. d) The NMs translocate in different tissues in the plant. e) After targeting specific tissue, the NMs respond to specific stimuli, such as pH, light, enzymes, ionic strength, and temperature (modified after Grillo et al. 2021¹⁵).

Transformation of materials in the environment or the human body goes beyond dissolution and agglomeration, to include (but not limited to) processes such as accumulation of other molecules onto the surface, modification of the surface chemistry and dissociation of components. All of these considerations are relevant to both NMs and AdMa.

For example, it is well known that when NMs enter the body of an organism, the surfaces of the particles are rapidly covered by biomolecules such as proteins, forming the so-called “protein corona”³¹. The same phenomenon can happen when NMs enter the environment, where they can be covered by natural organic matter (NOM). Little information is available on the formation of a NOM corona and the composition of the NOM corona on NMs in the environment due to limitations in analytical techniques. The protein corona consists of proteins which adsorb to the NM during a time span of a few minutes up to several hours³². The formation of a protein or NOM corona is dictated by the physicochemical properties of NMs such as size, aspect ratio, surface charge and chemical composition³³, as well as by the presence of the NOM or proteins in the surroundings and other conditions of the surroundings (pH, temperature etc).

For AdMa, the formation and evolution of a protein or NOM corona is probably also controlled by the physicochemical properties of the materials. We describe our expectation of protein corona formation on AdMa by using smart NMs as a model of AdMa in a hypothetical example of a polymeric particle with an iron NM core and a QD doped surface (Figure 3). In this illustration, we expect that different proteins adsorbed to the surface of the QD NM compare to the case of exposure of solely the polymeric NM in the same medium. It is also likely that activation of the iron NM with a magnetic field would generate heat³⁴ that can influence the formation of the protein corona (Figure 3).

Figure 3. A hypothetical example of a polymeric NM with a core iron NM and surface doped QDs. In the bloodstream, the particles are coated with protein to form a protein corona. The composition of the protein corona on the surface of the QD is different than the composition of the protein corona on the surface of the polymeric particles. When the particle is activated by a magnetic field, the iron particle in the core creates heat. We expect this heat to influence the composition of the protein corona on the surface of the polymeric particle.

Understanding the formation and evolution of protein or NOM corona are useful for hazard assessment. Sorption of biomolecules on the surface of AdMa confers a new biological identity to the materials, which influences the biological fate and biodistribution of the particles in various organs, tissues, and cells in organisms. For example, it is known that adsorption of proteins facilitates the recognition and uptake of particles by immune cells, which are involved in the uptake and metabolism of foreign particulates³⁵. We believe that while the existing data on protein corona formation on NMs can help to understand the corona formation on AdMa, alone it will not be sufficient. Some physicochemical properties of AdMa such as the multi-elemental composition and implementation of switchable properties in some AdMa, which imparts dynamic properties to the NMs, may add another dimension to the biological fate of AdMa, consequently complicating the prediction of their biodistribution and hazard.

Most of the available information on the elimination of NMs from the body is medically oriented and it is indicated that > 6 nm particles cannot be eliminated via renal excretion³⁶. Few (eco)toxicological studies on fish showed that NMs might be excreted from the gills^{37, 38}. Many promising AdMa have a size large than 6 nm³⁹. More studies are still needed to understand the uptake and elimination pathway of AdMa from different model organisms with (eco)toxicological purposes.

However, extensive characterization of pristine materials, in products or in various life cycle stages is not always practically feasible for many laboratories due to the extensive instrumentation and the skills required to perform the comprehensive characterization. These challenges have already been recognized for first generation of NMs, which apply to AdMa. Any characterisation should be attempted in a media that best represents the biological or environmental compartment relevant to the life cycle stage under consideration. There are some limitations that can further challenge the characterization of AdMa (including smart NMs). For example, the characterization of a multi-element AdMa consisting of inorganic and organic components requires combinations of techniques suitable for the characterization of each component (by assuming the sample preparation for the target component does not influence the other component of the AdMa). Moreover, it is yet unknown how to characterize the activity of smart AdMa upon stimulation for toxicological purposes, e.g. in nontarget organisms.

3. Being smart further challenges the toxicity testing of smart AdMa

Some AdMa are designed to undergo changes in their physicochemical properties in response to a specific stimulus. These are referred to as smart AdMa or smart NMs (although most of them have size larger than 100 nm). Examples of such AdMa include light-driven molecular motors and smart nano-pesticides. For example, it is possible to design nano-pesticides (Figure 2b) that minimize biocidal leaching. They thus reduce bioaccumulation in non-targeted organisms⁴⁰, which is a drawback of traditional pesticides. The nano-pesticides can be designed to target specific tissues in plants and remain passive (Figure 2c-d). They could be activated by stimuli such as pH or a specific enzyme¹⁵, leading to e.g. triggered and controlled cargo release in the target organisms. Similar AdMa have been developed for medical applications and for environmental remediation. These smart NMs might find their way to the market within a few years. Regardless of their terminologies, e.g. nanomachines, nanobiodevices, actuators, nanomotors and nanostructures, from a toxicological perspective

they are AdMa interacting with cells and biomolecules in organisms⁴¹. The question is what drives these interactions and what are the consequences for risk assessment.

There are few toxicological studies in which the effect of activated smart NMs has been investigated, although such tests are currently uncommon^{42, 43}. The question is whether and to what extent the smart or enhanced properties must be considered in toxicological studies. Hazard assessment based on the passive form of smart NMs is unlikely to be sufficient to assess their risk. The controlled functionality of smart NMs, therefore, adds another level of complexity to the toxicological studies of AdMa. Testing of the different forms of a material – passive and active – can be considered, but could be difficult to generate. It will also be difficult to assess and simulate the location of the bioavailability of active forms within the body or within cells. Also assessing the hazard of different forms would lead to higher costs for toxicity testing as well as a greater animal use. While guidelines and protocols exist for assessing hazards of dissolved chemicals, and in some cases for NMs, further work will be required to determine their suitability for the assessment of smart AdMa induced toxicity, and to make modifications if required.

4. Not all AdMa are NMs

For regulatory purposes, the EC recommended a definition for NMs in 2011 and the revision will be released soon⁴⁴. To enable safety assessment and management and implementation of regulation, the size range of 1-100 nm was proposed and adopted. Toxicity of materials is however not limited to a specific size, e.g. < 100 nm, and each organism and cell might respond differently to different sizes⁴⁵. It has for instance been shown that a particle with size larger than 100 nm might be more toxic than smaller counterparts of the same material⁴⁶. AdMa often exceed the threshold limit of 100 nm⁷. For example, many AdMa such as nanomotors and nanocomposites have sizes larger than 100 nm. This excludes them from being NMs according to the EC recommended definition despite having the term "Nano" in their terminologies. It is also likely that AdMa with sizes larger than 100 nm will be made of NMs with sizes smaller than 100 nm. Since not all AdMa are considered to be NMs and, thus, the nano-specific requirements are not applicable to all AdMa, these materials will not be regulated as NMs whereas physicochemical properties rather than chemical properties alone determine their fate/toxicokinetics and hazard. This may require new adaptations in regulations.

5. Can current (eco)toxicological guidelines cover AdMa?

The OECD and the ISO are working extensively on developing toxicological test guidelines (TGs) or Guidance Documents (GD)⁴⁷. From a regulatory perspective, these TGs and GDs are critical for current risk assessment procedures and support the international acceptance of data as well as harmonization across different labs and the generation of reliable data⁴⁸. Examples of published TG for NMs include TG 125 on particle size and particle size distribution, TG 413 of subchronic inhalation tests, and GD 317 on aquatic and sediment toxicological testing. These TGs or GDs have been newly developed for NMs or adapted from existing ones for chemicals^{49, 50}. Further work is ongoing for a number of other TGs and GDs. The increased complexity of AdMa, such as for the smart and multi-elemental AdMa, might further challenge the adequateness and fit-for-purpose of the TGs and GDs for NMs, which have been developed for mono-element NMs.

Recommendation for classification of AdMa for toxicological and risk assessment purposes

Given the anticipated developments of AdMa in the near future, it is important to consider how to address AdMa in legal frameworks, and if and what adaptations are needed to adequately gather information on safety to accommodate AdMa. Some AdMa will fall under the definition of NMs whereas others will not. Due to the large diversity in AdMa, it is useful to streamline assessing potential consequences of AdMa for physicochemical and (eco)toxicity testing by classification of AdMa into different groups. These groups should be based on their physicochemical properties that may involve similar mode-of-action of toxicity, e.g., the mode-of-action could include release of ions and particles of different types, surface area, etc. For example, in the clusters proposed by the German Environment Agency, advanced alloys and QD are classified into two different clusters. From a toxicological perspective, advanced alloys and QD could be particles consisting of more than one metal, where each metal within one particle might induce toxicity through similar pathways e.g., generating oxidative stress or cell apoptosis. The benefits of classification are to: (1) enable differentiation between AdMa based on their properties that might induce specific hazards, (2) provide measurable criteria that can be integrated into toxicological concepts, (3) provide clearer insight in what is needed to address AdMa in legal frameworks and (4) facilitate a faster pathway to identify the hazard of new AdMa.

Further refinements required to address the safety assessment of AdMa include:

- Investigate mode-of-action for each class of AdMa
- Consider when and how the existing information for single components can be used
- Consider how information on new or enhanced functionality can be used
- Consider how to address mixture effects of multicomponent AdMa

Currently, the Horizon Europe project SUNSHINE is developing approaches to address the toxicity of some AdMa and how existing information on single components or similar AdMa can be used in safety assessment (<https://www.h2020sunshine.eu/>). Unlike NMs, where strict adherence to a 100-nm size threshold has been proposed, we recommend not to limit the investigations on the toxicity of AdMa to particle sizes smaller than 100 nm. As we described earlier, it is highly likely that the size of AdMa will not be limited to the 100 nm threshold, some components of an AdMa may be smaller than 100 nm whereas the entire structure is not, and there is no scientific rationale related to safety for a strict cut-off at 100 nm⁵¹.

Summary and Recommendations

The identified challenges in toxicity and risk assessment of AdMa might go beyond the problems recognized for the first generation of NMs and even question the future of NM risk assessment. The European Chemicals Agency published an inventory of new AdMa⁶. There is no doubt that the number of AdMa on the market will increase in the future. An important step to support technological development, in general, is the implementation of a safe-and-sustainable-by-design (SSbD) strategy. The AdMa-based technologies will benefit from the identification of potential risks and sustainability issues associated with AdMa as of the early stages of innovation to support the SSbD development, and the production, use, and end-of-life treatment of the materials³. A systematic early warning system has been proposed and established jointly by the Dutch National Institute of Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) and German agencies (UBA, BfR, BAUA) to identify potential risks and

sustainability issues of advanced NMs which can also be applied to AdMa in general. Moreover, within OECD, an early warning system is under development.

It is critical now to support (eco)toxicological studies of AdMa and to advance toxicology to tackle the challenges associated with the development of innovative AdMa. The generated data are important in order to be able to assess the risk of AdMa and to gather information to support the early warning systems, grouping and SSbD. The hazard assessment of a variety of AdMa may need to expand because new toxicological phenomena, which are not covered by the classical (apical) endpoints, might be induced by AdMa. We finally recommend the development of an efficient network between innovators, researchers and policy-makers, where up-to-date findings are transferred to facilitate the development of regulations for AdMa.

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Author contributions

F.A.M. conceptualized, supervised, wrote, and reviewed the Perspective. W.J.G., V.S, E.V.J, A.O, J.V.K.K contributed to the conceptualization, writing and edition of the Perspective. R.K., J.K., J.A., P.Z., and A.S contributed to the editing of the Perspective.

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